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Good practice guide

Recommendations for instruments requirements,
characterization and calibration of array spectroradiometers
used as spectral irradiance transfer standard instruments

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1. Scope

This Good Practice Guide reviews properties of array spectroradiometers relevant for their use as spectral irradiance transfer standards and the established techniques for their characterization and calibration. Recommendations for specifications for array spectroradiometer to be used as transfer standards are given, which are applicable at least in the spectral range between 250 nm and 2500 nm.

2. Definitions

Irradiance: Density of incident radiant flux with respect to area at a point on a real or imaginary surface. The irradiance is expressed in $W \cdot m^{-2}$ (see also CIE S017:2020 ILV, 17-21-053 [CIE 2020 1]).

Spectral irradiance: Density of the irradiance with respect to wavelength. The spectral irradiance is expressed in $W \cdot m^{-2} \cdot nm^{-1}$ (see also CIE S017:2020 ILV, 17-21-056 [CIE 2020 1]).

Realization of the (spectral) irradiance quantity: Procedure allowing either (1) producing a well determined (spectral) irradiance, or (2) to determine the (spectral) irradiance on a specific plane. The case (1) is usually based on radiant sources, while the case (2) is based on detectors.

Dissemination of the (spectral) irradiance: A procedure allowing the comparison of (spectral) irradiance measurements with a measurement standard representing the (spectral) irradiance quantity.

Measurement standard: Realization of the definition of a given quantity, with stated quantity value and associated measurement uncertainty, used as a reference (see JCGM200:2012 5.1 [JCGM 2012]).

Primary standard: Measurement standard established using a primary reference measurement procedure, or created as an artefact, chosen by convention (JCGM200:2012 5.4 [JCGM 2012]). For (spectral) irradiance primary standards are represented by blackbody radiators, synchrotron radiation or cryogenic radiometers.

Transfer standard: Standard whose quantities are determined by measurements (calibration) traceable to a primary standard, and which allows the relevant quantity to be transferred.

Spectral irradiance transfer standard spectroradiometer (ITSS): Spectroradiometer with long-term stability, whose spectral responsivity is traceable to a primary standard (via calibrations), such that it can be used for the dissemination of the spectral irradiance quantity.

3. General considerations

3.1. Transference of the spectral irradiance

The specific requirements for a spectral irradiance transfer standard spectroradiometer (ITSS) are those *allowing the spectral irradiance quantity to be transferred while avoiding a notable increase of the relative uncertainty in the **transferred spectral irradiance** with respect to the **reference spectral irradiance**.*

In a first stage, the spectral responsivity of the transfer standard spectroradiometer needs to be determined by measurements with metrological traceability to a primary standard. The spectral responsivity calibration also includes characterizations of the ITSS that are necessary to establish corrections and associated uncertainty contributions from all relevant instrumental parameters. In a second stage, the characterized and calibrated spectroradiometer will transfer the quantity to another spectroradiometer by measuring the spectral irradiance of other radiant sources at the user site. The spectral distribution of these radiant sources will differ from that of the reference used in the first stage. The associated measurement uncertainties are affected by dissimilarities between the radiant sources and other measurement conditions, which need to be estimated using the results of the ITSS characterizations carried out in the first stage.

The ITSS might also be used as a working standard for spectral irradiance measurements in end-user applications, but only if the ITSS has the properties required for the specific applications. For example, the ITSS which is conceived exclusively for transferring the spectral irradiance, have lower requirements regarding bandpass than an instrument used in applications featuring narrow spectral features like photobiological safety (steep action spectra) or solar irradiance (steep gradients and some narrow absorption features). In these cases, the ITSS should not be used as the working standard.

The process of transferring the spectral irradiance with an array spectroradiometer is exemplified in Annex A with some figures based on simulations, obtained by using a simple model of response for array spectroradiometers.

3.2. Main components of an array spectroradiometer

Array spectroradiometers are sophisticated instruments designed to measure spectral irradiance or other spectral radiant quantities across a wide range of wavelengths simultaneously. These instruments integrate multiple key components that work together to capture and analyse light, from input optics to detector arrays.

- **Input optics:** The light collection system of a spectroradiometer typically begins with diffusers or integrating spheres that ensure uniform light collection for precise spectral irradiance measurements. They are either directly attached to the spectrometer or are followed by fiber-optic cables with specialized connectors that transmit the collected light while maintaining signal integrity. The light is then coupled to the entrance slit, which regulates the amount of light entering the instrument and plays a crucial role in determining spectral resolution. Collimation optics may also be present to create parallel light beams for optimal dispersion.
- **Dispersive element:** Typically a diffraction grating, this component separates the incoming light into its constituent wavelengths. The grating's groove density and blaze angle are crucial factors in determining the instrument's spectral resolution and responsivity.
- **Focusing optics:** These elements focus the dispersed light onto the detector array. They may include optics designed to minimize aberrations and optimize spectral imaging.
- **Detector array:** Typically a linear array of photosensitive elements, often a Charge-Coupled Device (CCD) or Complementary Metal-Oxide-Semiconductor (CMOS) sensor. Each pixel in the array corresponds to a specific wavelength range, allowing simultaneous measurement of the entire spectrum.
- **Electronics and signal processing:** This includes analog-to-digital converters, readout circuitry, and often on-board processors for initial data handling and correction algorithms.
- **Temperature control system:** Many high-precision instruments incorporate active cooling systems, such as Peltier elements, to stabilize the detector temperature and reduce thermal noise.
- **Housing and shielding:** A robust, sometimes thermally stabilized, enclosure protects the optical and electronic components from environmental influences and electromagnetic interference.
- **Calibration features:** Some instruments include internal wavelength calibration sources (e.g., mercury-argon lamps) or light traps for dark signal measurements.
- **Software systems:** These specialized systems process raw spectral data, apply calibration factors, and convert detector signals into meaningful radiometric quantities. Modern spectroradiometer software typically offers comprehensive tools for spectral analysis, interactive data visualization, and versatile export options to facilitate further data processing in external applications.

The design and quality of these components significantly influence the instrument's performance characteristics, including spectral range, resolution, responsivity, and stability. For instance, the choice between a CCD and CMOS detector can affect factors like dynamic range and readout time.

Advanced array spectroradiometers may also incorporate additional features such as automatic exposure control, stray light correction algorithms, and interfaces for external accessories like optical fibers or integrating spheres.

Understanding the structure and components of array spectroradiometers is very important for proper instrument selection, operation, and maintenance, ensuring optimal performance across various spectroradiometric applications, from solar UV monitoring to color and display measurements.

3.3. Characterization and calibration

Array spectroradiometer characterization and calibration involve comprehensive techniques to ensure accurate spectral measurements, addressing critical aspects such as radiometric calibration, wavelength accuracy, linearity, polarization sensitivity, noise characteristics, temperature dependence, detector aging, dark signal correction, stray light effects, and uncertainty quantification. These methodologies include advanced calibration models, Monte Carlo uncertainty analysis, stray light correction strategies, and assessment of key parameters that impact measurement accuracy and reliability across diverse applications from laboratory research to field monitoring.

4. Relevant spectroradiometer properties

The selection of spectroradiometers for use as transfer standard spectroradiometer for spectral irradiance depends on the instrument properties. The relevant spectroradiometer properties are listed in Table 1. Some of these properties need to be characterized and corrected to provide traceable measurements and uncertainty through their use in the measurement model. The characterization and calibration data together with the measurement model implementation of the array spectroradiometer represent the digital twin of the transfer standard instrument. The properties requiring characterizations are indicated in the table with an asterisk (*).

Table 1. Relevant properties for transfer standard spectroradiometers.

Property	Description	References to characterization methods **
Quantifiable properties		
<i>Spectral properties</i>		
* Spectral responsivity	Ratio of the instrument indications to the input spectral irradiance.	[Kostkowski 1997, Hopkinson 2004, CIE2019]
Spectral range	Range of wavelength for which the instrument provides a signal usable for measurement.	[CIE 2019]
Sampling interval	The difference between two consecutive output wavelengths.	[CIE 2019]
* Optical resolution, or spectral bandwidth (SBW)	The area under the bandpass curve divided by the height at the nominal centre wavelength. For a symmetric triangle or trapezoid bandpass function, the spectral bandpass is equivalent to the full-width at half maximum (FWHM) of the bandpass function. It is related to the physical slit-width and optical dispersion of the monochromator system. The spectral bandwidth (SBW) together with the sampling interval determines the spectral resolution of a measurement which is often given as the FWHM of the SBW.	[Seckmeyer 2001, Brown 2003, Hopkinson 2004, Ylianttila 2005, Zong 2006, Woolliams 2011, Zong 2012, CIE 2014, CIE 2019, Zuber 2020, Li 2022]
*Internal stray light	Signal produced by optical radiation entering the instrument and reaching the detector at a wavelength other than the wavelength intended to be measured. It is produced by scattering within the instrument, reflections, higher diffractions orders, etc. It produces error in the measurement result.	[Hopkinson 2004, Brown 2003, Ylianttila 2005, Zong 2006, Li 2022, Zuber 2020, CIE 2019]
<i>Properties for operation signal range</i>		
Dynamic range	Ratio of maximum and minimum signal levels, that can be reproduced with an incremental signal-to-noise ratio of at least 1.	[CIE 2022]
*Linearity	Quality of the spectral responsivity to be independent of the input irradiance. The deviation from linearity (non-linearity) must be determined for the full usable range of instrument indications.	[Kostkowski 1997, Hopkinson 2004, CIE 2019, Eppeldauer 2020, CIE 2020]
*Dark signal	Signal for nominally zero irradiance input. For array spectroradiometers, it depends on the integration time, is different for each pixel and will often change with the temperature of the detector array. Readout noise refers to a random variation of null average which is a component of the dark signal. It is generated at the readout stage, and is independent of the level of the signal and other parameters as the integration time or the number or class of the readout electrons.	[Hopkinson 2004, CIE 2022]

Property	Description	References to characterization methods **
Noise Equivalent Irradiance (NEI)	Spectral irradiance that produces an output equal to the root mean square (RMS) noise output.	17-25-071 in [CIE 2020 1]
<i>Sensitivity properties</i>		
*Angular dependence	Sensitivity of the instrument responsivity to different incidence angles of irradiation.	[CIE 2022]
Uniformity	Sensitivity of the instrument to different positions of irradiation on the entrance optic.	[CIE 2022]
Sensitivity to polarization	Sensitivity of the instrument to different polarization states of the incident radiant flux. Common input optics of spectroradiometers measuring spectral irradiance (diffusers, integrating spheres) are typically polarization-insensitive making the instrument insensitive to polarization as well.	[CIE 2022], [CIE 2019]
*Sensitivity to temperature	Sensitivity of the instrument responsivity and wavelength scale to ambient temperature changes.	[CIE 2022]
Sensitivity to relative humidity	Sensitivity of the instrument responsivity to changes in the relative humidity of ambient air.	
Sensitivity to blooming	Sensitivity of the instrument to blooming. Blooming is when the charge in a pixel exceeds the saturation level and the charge starts to fill adjacent pixels.	
Sensitivity to leakage	Sensitivity of the instrument to leakage of charges during the readout time. It produces smear in CCD sensors when the integration time is much lower than the readout time.	[Ferrero 2006 2]
<i>Stability properties</i>		
Repeatability	Closeness of agreement between the results of successive measurements, carried out under the same measurement conditions, i.e. the same measurements procedure, observer, conditions and laboratory at relatively short intervals of time.	
Wavelength stability	Stability of wavelength-to-pixel correspondence in the array on a defined time interval.	
Radiometric stability	Stability of the responsivity on a defined time interval.	
Descriptive properties		
Transportability	In this context, the quality of being transportable within and out the laboratory without affecting the calibration.	
Digital interface	The available level of control on the acquisitions (raw or processed readouts from every pixel, manual or automated, local or remote, etc..).	

* To be characterized for traceable measurements and uncertainty estimation through the measurement model. Required inputs for the digital twin.

5. Requirements for array spectroradiometers to be used as transfer standard spectroradiometers

The requirements stated below are categorized as:

- **General:** Requirements for an array spectroradiometer to be qualified as transfer standard spectroradiometer.
- **Specific requirements for ITSSs:** They are specifically relevant for ITSS. Quantitative requirements are not given but implicitly as a reference to the uncertainty of the transfer radiant source standard.
- **Specific requirements for end-user applications:** They are additional requirements, and in consequence, are more restrictive requirements.

5.1. General requirements

There are some general requirements for an array spectroradiometer to be qualified as transfer standard spectroradiometer for spectral irradiance:

1. Spectral responsivity and wavelength scale stable on a timescale appropriate for a practical dissemination of the spectral irradiance unit (typically months).
2. Input optics suitable for the measurement of spectral irradiance.
3. Adequate spectral range.
4. Digital interface enabling the automated control and readout of the instrument
5. Transportable.
6. Insensitive to small temperature and humidity changes. Preferably, active temperature stabilization of the detector.
7. Access to raw signals that calibrations (wavelength and responsivity values) or corrections are assigned to.

5.2. Specific requirements for ITSSs

Some of the properties given in Table 1 will be examined below. The specific quantitative requirements should refer to the relative uncertainty of the reference radiant source for the spectral irradiance ($u_{\text{ref,rel}}$), because it is not possible to decrease this uncertainty by a better determination of other parameters. The relative uncertainty component from a given single source error 'e', uncorrelated with $u_{\text{ref,rel}}$ and with value $u_{\text{e,rel}} = u_{\text{ref,rel}}/n$, will increase the combined relative uncertainty by a factor $f_u = \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{1}{n}\right)^2}$. An overall increase over $u_{\text{ref,rel}}$ by about 1% ($n > \sim 7$) can in general be regarded as negligible. For overall expanded uncertainties in the ITSS-based transfer of spectral irradiance on the order of 1%, as aimed for in the NEWSTAND project), individual relative uncertainty components below about 0.15% would then be regarded "negligible". Still, also "negligible" uncertainty components should be quantitatively estimated and tracked as the contributions of many "negligible" components might sum up to a significant contribution to the overall measurement uncertainty.

Spectral bandwidth: The larger the spectral bandwidth, the larger is the error in the measurement. This error, which is zero for ideally constant or linearly changing spectral distributions within the bandpass, increases with increasing steepness of the gradient of a spectral distribution. In the case of array spectroradiometers, the shape, symmetry and width of the bandpass function can change with wavelength. As a result, the measured spectral irradiance values can be severely affected. Ideally, an ITSS should have a narrow and symmetrical bandpass function that changes little across the spectral range. In most cases, a FWHM of 2 nm is sufficient, but it depends on the end-user application and the type of radiation source used in instrument calibrations for the transfer measurements. The ITSS shall be able to measure the spectral distribution of the reference spectral distribution without increasing notably the uncertainty either without bandpass correction or after applying spectral bandwidth corrections. As the measurement result by a spectroradiometer is represented by a convolution of the spectral bandpass function and the spectral power distribution, bandpass correction is generally required for the accurate measurement of spectral irradiance and often also for the accurate determination of spectral integrals.

Spectral responsivity: The spectral responsivity needs to be large enough over the spectral range to allow accurate measurement of the spectral irradiance needed to be transferred in a time interval adequate for the application.

Linearity: Any deviation from proportionality between input quantity and output signals (non-linearity) needs to be on the level of $0.3 \times u_{\text{ref,rel}}$ or less, which usually will require applying corrections. Usually, the availability of raw data allows for a more accurate characterization, and, consequently, correction. If raw data is not accessible, the method of correction should be described.

Dynamic range: A dynamic range of at least 10000 is recommended. This number represents the ratio between the maximum usable response and the dark noise. This will in principle allow typical stray light levels even for good instruments to be characterized, and allow sources under conditions similar to using FEL-lamps as calibration sources to be measured, where it is needed to deal with variations of about two orders of magnitude in signal levels and up to another two orders of magnitude in responsivity (for grating based instruments) over the measurement range (e.g. VIS). In principle, when there is no blooming, there is always the possibility of extending the dynamic range by using high-dynamic-range (HDR) algorithms, in which case this property is less relevant for ITSS.

Dark signal: It should be stable enough to be subtracted. That is, the variation of the mean dark signal between measurements has to be at least a factor of three smaller than the uncertainty of the determination of the mean dark signal. The main contributions to dark signal are thermally-generated electrons and spurious electrons generated as part of the charge-transfer and readout processes of the detector. Properly characterized, the mean dark signal can be subtracted but the uncertainty of this characterization (e.g. shot noise of thermally-generated electrons, n_{th} and readout noise n_{read}) can contribute significantly to the noise of the measurement when the number of photogenerated electrons (n_{ph}) is of similar order than n_{th} or n_{read} . This, in combination with a realistic time of measurement, imposes a limitation on the minimum level of irradiance measurable by ITSS with an uncertainty negligible with respect to $u_{\text{ref,rel}}$. The thermal contribution to the dark signal is in general dependent on the chosen integration time. For proper mean dark signal subtraction, the mean dark signal has to be determined for the same integration time as the subsequent measurement.

Internal stray light: Internal stray light is radiation that propagates inside the measurement instrument and reaches the detector in an unwanted manner, e.g. by inter-reflection or diffuse scattering. Importantly, the effect of the internal stray light depends on the relative spectral distribution of the source and the ITSS itself. The internal stray light can be reduced by e.g. bandpass filters or numerically by a correction. Different characterization and correction methods exist. As a rule of thumb, the stray light contribution is significant at signals that are several orders of magnitude smaller than the maximum signal level. Internal stray light acts as a (spectrally variable) signal-offset, that depends on the stray-light characteristics of the ITSS as well as the spectral distribution of the source measured. As another rule of thumb, the ratio of the instrument signal saturation level to the maximum corresponding (corrected) stray-light signal should be at least equal to the dynamic range of the instrument. In this case stray-light will not contribute significantly to the measurement at low signal-levels even if the stray-light generating signal-levels approach saturation.

Radiometric stability: An ITSS should be stable and reproducible in its radiometric characteristics. It is important to note that the input optics are an integral part of the spectroradiometer. Therefore, detaching (fiber-coupled) input optics may lead to changes in the responsivity and void the calibration. The relative variation of the response under identical measurement conditions needs to be negligible with respect to $u_{\text{ref,rel}}$.

Sampling interval: The sampling interval should be small enough for the instrument to acquire at least four data samples per FWHM of the SBW in order to allow for characterization of the instrument SBW and accurate interpolation of measurement data.

Angular dependence: No angular dependence is desired around the range of incidence angles used typically in transfer measurements. For the specified range of angles of incidence, the uncertainty contribution due to imperfect cosine correction should be negligible with respect to $u_{\text{ref,rel}}$. We recommend deviations from perfect cosine response lower than 0.1% for angles up to 5° , since for typical currently used calibration geometries with FEL lamps angles larger than 5° are typically rare, except for very large irradiance samples. The requirement above will typically be easily fulfilled with good standard irradiance input optics.

Sensitivity to polarization: No sensitivity to polarization is desired if the selected transfer standard sources are somehow polarized. We recommend a polarization sensitivity smaller than 1% - 2% (maximum relative

variation of the measurement signal over a 90° rotation of a fully linear polarized source), which is typically intrinsically achieved with diffuser-based input optics. For a partially polarized radiant source with a degree of polarization of up to about 10 % - 20 % this would still not lead to a significant increase in the measurement uncertainties (lower than 1%, $k = 2$). If sensitivity to polarization is significant, the use of highly polarized sources would for many reasons probably be problematic and will require special attention.

Sensitivity to changes in ambient conditions: Sensitivity of instrument spectral responsivity and wavelength scale to changes in ambient conditions (temperature, humidity) should be small enough to allow accurate transfer of the spectral irradiance unit under typical laboratory conditions. The uncertainty contributions due to changes of the instrument properties with ambient conditions should be negligible with respect to $u_{\text{ref,rel}}$ over a temperature range from 20°C to 30°C and relative humidities ranging from 30% to 70%. Depending on the instrument used, this might require corrections.

Reference plane: The reference plane of the input optics, often given by a limiting aperture, should be available or feasible to be determined from the mechanical design. The measurement distance should be chosen such that the relative error induced by the uncertainty in the reference plane position is negligible. As an example, with a typical measurement distance d of 500 mm, a +1 mm error e in d would lead to a relative error of 0.4 % in the irradiance due to the relative difference between d^2 and $(d + e)^2$, whereas a +0.5 mm error in d would lead to a relative error of 0.2 % in irradiance.

5.3. Specific requirements for end-user applications

In this case, the specific quantitative requirements should be referred to the targeted relative uncertainty of the measurement aimed at the specific application. This targeted uncertainty has to be always larger than $U_{\text{ref,rel}}$.

Spectral solar (UV) measurements: See [Gröbner 2005, Hülsen 2016, Blumthaler 2013]. Good cosine response of the input optics is especially important in this application. Also, the requirements on the instrument bandpass, stray light, and ambient sensitivity will typically be more strict.

Solar cells: Similar requirements as for spectral solar measurements.

Photobiological safety: SBW requirements (or the need for bandpass correction) as well as dynamic range and stray-light requirements will often be stricter than the general requirements given above.

Colorimetry: Accurate colorimetric measurements require a very good stray-light performance as well as high accuracy of the wavelength scale

Recommendations for different applications

The Table 2 provides some recommendations, as a good practice selection guide for suited array spectroradiometers for specific applications.

Table 2. Recommendations for different applications.

Property	Transfer standard spectroradiometer	Spectral solar measurements	Solar cells	UV measurements	Photometric measurements
Optical resolution, or spectral bandwidth (SBW)	The small gradients of the spectral distributions of reference sources makes the SBW error negligible for moderate FWHMs.	<1 nm (280 nm - 400 nm) <3 nm (400 nm - 1100 nm) 5 nm - 10 nm (at longer wavelengths), or correction according to CIE214 needed		<1 nm (280 nm - 400 nm) or correction according to CIE 214 needed	<5 nm (360 nm to 830 nm) or correction according to CIE 214 needed
Spectral range	Determined by the adequate range for the end-application.	From 270 nm to > 2500 nm (270 nm - 400 nm for solar UV measurements)	From 280 nm to 1200 nm (Si single junction or Si/Perotandem) From 280 nm to 1700 nm for multi-junction cells	From 280 nm to 400 nm.	From 360 nm to 830 nm
Stray light correction (internal stray light)	Depends on spectral range and optical radiation sources used for calibration and application. Stray-light correction is recommended whenever the inverse of the relative stray-light level is expected to be smaller than the dynamic range of the measurement				
Non-linearity	The related error should not be the dominant source of uncertainty. A relative maximum deviation from proportionality lower than 1 % is typically enough for target expanded uncertainties of that order of magnitude.				
Dynamic range	It has to cover all sources measured (during calibration and application). At least 8 orders of magnitude in the irradiance range and 4 orders of magnitude in the signal range are recommended.				
Sampling interval (nm per pixel)	In general, the adequate sampling interval depends on the spectral bandwidth. The use of 1/3 of spectral bandwidth for the sampling interval is typically sufficient.				
Angular dependence	Only relevant when the transfer conditions require a very extended and nearby sources. This is the case of applications as solar cells , spectral solar and photobiological safety measurements .				
Sensitivity to ambient conditions	Only relevant when the transfer condition requires a very different and uncontrolled environment than in the calibration. This is the case of field measurements, as spectral solar measurements .				

6. Characterization, correction and calibration procedures

The procedures described in this chapter are classified as:

- **Fundamental:** These are the main procedures required to characterize and calibrate spectroradiometers and consist of:
 - Wavelength calibration
 - Responsivity calibration
 - Spectral bandwidth and internal stray light characterization
 - Linearity characterization and correction
 - Dark signal and external stray light subtraction
 - Position of the reference plane in the input optics
- **Secondary**
 - **General:** Recommended generally for usual radiometric measurements.
 - **Complementary:** Convenient to complement the knowledge of the instrument to avoid its use in inadequate conditions.
 - **Additional** for specific end-user applications.

6.1. Fundamental procedures

1. **Wavelength calibration** [Hopkinson 2004, Gaigalas 2009, Kostkowski 1997, CIE 2019, CIE 2022, CIE 2014, Zong 2017, Martinsen 2008]

Wavelength calibration is a fundamental aspect of array spectroradiometer characterization, ensuring accurate assignment of spectral features to specific wavelengths. This process is critical for maintaining measurement accuracy across the instrument's entire spectral range.

The primary method for wavelength calibration involves measuring a limited number (typically 10-20) of narrow spectral emission lines with known wavelengths [Zong 2017]. These emission lines are often provided by gas discharge lamps, such as mercury-argon or neon lamps, which offer well-defined spectral features across the UV-VIS-NIR range.

The calibration process typically follows these steps:

1. Measure the spectrum of the wavelength calibration source
2. Determine centroid positions of reference spectral features in pixel space
3. Assign known wavelengths to these pixel positions
4. Inter-/extrapolate set of pixel positions and reference wavelengths to full pixels scale. Accurate interpolation of data can in general be achieved by a low order polynomial function. Be aware that the extrapolation might cause errors.

Advanced calibration techniques may employ tunable laser systems or monochromators to provide precise wavelength calibration across the entire spectral range. This method allows for a more detailed characterization of the instrument's spectral response function and can significantly reduce uncertainties in wavelength assignment.

Temperature effects on wavelength calibration are substantial and must be carefully controlled. Thermal expansion or contraction of optical components can lead to shifts in the wavelength scale. To address this, many high-precision instruments incorporate temperature monitoring and compensation algorithms.

The accuracy of wavelength calibration directly impacts the overall measurement uncertainty. High-accuracy calibration methods can achieve uncertainties as low as 0.05 nm for wavelengths between 380 nm and 980 nm [Gaigalas 2009]. However, the uncertainty typically increases at the extremes of the instrument's spectral range.

Regular verification and adjustment of wavelength calibration are essential to maintain measurement accuracy over time. This is particularly important for field instruments exposed to varying environmental conditions. Some advanced systems incorporate internal wavelength calibration sources for on-site verification and adjustment.

By implementing robust wavelength calibration techniques and regular verification procedures, array spectroradiometer users can ensure accurate spectral measurements across a wide range of applications, from solar UV monitoring to color and display measurements.

2. Spectral responsivity calibration [Hopkinson 2004, Kostkowski 1997, CIE 2019, CIE 2022]

The spectral responsivity is a crucial aspect of array spectroradiometer characterization that significantly impacts measurement accuracy and reliability. The spectral responsivity describes how the instrument responds to spectral irradiance at different wavelengths. It relates the net spectral response (dark, internal and external stray light signals subtracted) of the spectroradiometer to a known spectral irradiance that is metrologically traceable to a primary standard. This standard source can be realized by either a spectrally broadband source or by spectrally tunable laser systems or monochromators generating spectrally narrow-bandwidth output at precise wavelengths. The resulting spectral responsivity is essential for understanding the instrument's capabilities and limitations, particularly in regions where sensitivity may be lower, such as the ultraviolet or near-infrared.

The spectral response function is typically represented as:

$$R(\lambda) = \frac{S(\lambda)}{E(\lambda)} \quad (1)$$

Where $R(\lambda)$ is the spectral responsivity, $S(\lambda)$ is the measured dark-subtracted response, and $E(\lambda)$ is the known spectral irradiance of the calibration source.

3. Spectral bandpass and internal stray light characterization [Hopkinson 2004, Brown 2003, Ylianttila 2005, Zong 2006, Li 2022, Zuber 2019, Zuber 2020, CIE 2014, CIE 2019]

Internal stray light is a significant source of measurement error in array spectroradiometers, affecting the accuracy and reliability of spectral measurements. This phenomenon occurs when optical radiation from a specific wavelength is detected at a different instrumental wavelength as well, leading to distortions in the measured spectral distributions.

Since the spectral range of an array spectroradiometer may be narrower than that of its detector, internal stray light is categorized as follows:

- **Out-of-range stray light:** Light at wavelengths outside the nominal spectral range of the instrument that reaches the detector and can be detected by it.
- **In-range stray light:** Stray light from wavelengths within the instrument's spectral range.

The impact of internal stray light is particularly noticeable in measurements which need a high dynamic range or when measuring weak signals in the presence of strong spectral features at different wavelength or broader spectral distributions with dynamic range. For instance, in solar UV measurements, stray light can lead to significant overestimation of irradiance in the UV-B region due to the much stronger UV-A and visible light contamination. If the relative spectral distributions of the sources used in ITSS calibration measurement and transfer calibration measurement are very similar, also stray light will affect both measurements in a similar way and associated measurement errors will largely cancel. In such a situation, accurate transfer calibrations can be achieved also without stray light correction of the ITSS.

To characterize in-range stray light the general procedure is monochromatic characterization of the spectroradiometer and by acquiring the signal over the whole spectral range of the instruments, yielding the wavelength dependent Line Spread Function (LSF). If the spectral bandwidth of the monochromatic source is narrow enough, the LSF measurement describes both the spectral bandpass of the instrument and the internal stray light. Acquiring the LSFs over the whole spectral range allows corrections to be determined both for the bandpass function and for the stray light with the help of a so-called stray light correction matrix [CIE214:2014].

For stray light characterization and correction, simplified approaches based on long-pass and band-pass filters can be used under certain conditions and applications [CIE 2019, Li 2022].

Out-of-range stray light can be characterized and corrected using long-pass filters. Filter-based correction methods have been developed and implemented also to simultaneously address both in-range and out-of-range stray light, providing more comprehensive correction [Zuber 2019].

It's important to note that stray light characteristics can change due to factors such as temperature fluctuations, aging of optical components, and mechanical stress. Therefore, regular stray light characterization and correction are essential for maintaining measurement accuracy.

4. **Linearity characterization and correction** [Eppeldauer 2020, CIE 2019, CIE 2020, Hopkinson 2004, Kostkowski 1997]

Linearity refers to the proportionality between the dark-subtracted response of the array spectroradiometer and irradiance. It determines the instrument's ability to accurately measure sources with varying intensities. It also can be expressed as a constancy of the responsivity for different irradiance levels.

The complete characterization of the non-linearity of array spectroradiometers is typically done using a double-aperture method, and in some cases by comparing measurements at different integration times, depending on the instrument [CIE 2020].

To characterize linearity, measurements are taken at various input intensities, often achieved by varying the distance from a stable light source or using neutral density filters. The relationship between dark-subtracted response and irradiance is considered linear when it can be expressed as:

$$S = k E \quad (2)$$

where S is the dark subtracted response, E is the irradiance and k is the proportionality factor.

Deviations from linearity are quantified and, if significant, corrected through mathematical models or lookup tables. For high-precision applications, linearity correction can be applied on a per-pixel basis to account for variations across the detector array. By thoroughly characterizing and correcting for spectral response and linearity, array spectroradiometers can achieve high levels of accuracy and reliability across a wide range of measurement scenarios, from laboratory-based research to challenging field applications in environmental monitoring and industrial quality control.

There are several methods in the literature for characterizing optical detector systems, being the most contrasted: superposition, combinatorial, attenuation and differential spectral responsivity (DSR) [Eppeldauer 2020, CIE 2020]. The methods proposed in [Eppeldauer 2020, CIE 2020] are adequate for assessing linearity of spectroradiometers. However, the above-mentioned methods address only the linearity with respect to the irradiance. There is a non-linearity with respect to the readout electronics at the pixels of the array spectroradiometer, which is proportional to the radiant exposure (radiant flux by exposure time). This means that the responsivity can depend on the integration time and on the direct response of the instrument (counts or digital number (DN)), in addition to the irradiance [CIE 2019, Ferrero 2006 2]. These dependencies must be evaluated and avoided or corrected if possible before evaluating the non-linearity with respect to the irradiance. A simple procedure to evaluate the non-linearity with respect to direct response is, for instance [Ferrero 2006, Pacheco-Labrador 2014]. The corrected direct net response, expressed in units of count / s, DN / s or similar will be (within the uncertainty of the correction) proportional to irradiance.

5. **Dark signal and external stray light subtraction** [Hopkinson 2004]

Dark signal is a critical parameter in array spectroradiometer characterization, representing the response produced by the detector in the absence of incident optical radiation. This intrinsic noise significantly impacts measurement accuracy, especially in low-light conditions or when measuring weak signals.

The dark signal primarily originates from two sources:

- **Thermal dark signal:** Electrons generated by thermal energy within the detector, increasing with temperature.
- **Electronic or readout noise:** Inherent noise from the readout circuitry and other electronic components.

Accurate dark signal correction is essential for obtaining reliable spectral measurements. Two methods are employed for dark signal determination and correction:

- Direct contemporaneous measurements: This involves acquiring the dark signal immediately before or after the acquisition at irradiance conditions. This method accounts for short-term variations in dark signal but may increase measurement time. Some instruments incorporate mechanisms to block light from reaching the detector, allowing for real-time dark signal measurements.
- Modelling: Dark signal can be modeled as a function of integration time and temperature. This approach allows for faster measurements but requires careful characterization of the detector's behavior under various conditions.

Temperature plays a crucial role in dark signal behavior, since it affects the value of the thermal dark signal. Thermal dark signal decreases with detector temperature. Many high-precision spectroradiometers use active cooling systems to maintain a constant and low detector temperature. In addition, there are advanced algorithms which adjust dark signal correction based on temperature monitoring.

For prolonged measurements, dark output noise drift can become significant. Recent research has developed improved methods for compensating this drift, enhancing measurement accuracy over extended periods [Zhao 2023].

In practice, dark signal correction involves subtracting the measured or modeled dark signal from the acquisitions at irradiance conditions. This process must be performed carefully to ensure effective correction without introducing additional errors. If a modeled dark signal is subtracted, a regular characterization of dark signal behavior is crucial, as it can change over time due to detector aging or environmental factors. This typically involves measuring dark signals at various integration times and temperatures to create comprehensive correction models.

The external stray light signal can be regarded, similarly to the dark signal, as a signal not related to the irradiance being measured. However, whereas the additional signal is generated by the detector itself in the case of the dark signal, external stray light signal is generated by other light sources or unwanted optical pathways from the light source to the input optics. This stray light needs to be minimized and/or characterized using baffles and subtracted. Minimizing external stray light is achieved by baffles limiting the field of view of the input optics as much as possible to the radiant extent of the source to be measured. Characterizing stray light requires a complimentary baffle configuration, where at best only the part of the field of view containing the radiant extent of the source is blocked.

6. Position of the reference plane in the input optics [ISO/CIE 2014]

The spectral irradiance responsivity calibration of the spectroradiometer requires knowledge of the position of the reference plane, i.e. the position of an effective radiometric aperture in the input optics. The reference plane may be defined by a mechanical aperture limiting the sensitive area of the input optics. Otherwise, it can be determined experimentally. The procedures described in [ISO/CIE 2014] for planar, spherical and cylindrical illuminance meters are applicable here.

For the determination of the reference plane, the spectroradiometer input optics is irradiated under constant radiant intensity at different distances, d , and the average net signals, S , are acquired. The hypothesis is that the reference plane is that for which the inverse-square law holds. Therefore, the equation is

$$S = \frac{I}{(d + \delta)^2} \quad (3)$$

with I an empirical parameter used to obtain the distance offset δ . The δ represents the distance offset of the instrument's reference plane from which the distance d is measured. Any offset on the source side will add to δ . The analysis can be simplified by plotting the inverse of the square root of the measured signal as a function of the measurement distance. The intercept of the line represents the distance offset δ . The characterization can additionally be simplified by employing a reference detector with a well-defined reference plane position, i.e. a mechanical aperture as a radiometric aperture stop. Taking the difference between the determined distance offsets for the spectroradiometer input optics and for the reference detector eliminates the need to know the exact position of the source.

6.2. Secondary procedures

General procedures

There are secondary procedures which are generally recommended for usual radiometric measurement applications.

- Evaluation of temporal stability and reproducibility of the spectroradiometer spectral responsivity and wavelength scale. Both the spectral responsivity and the wavelength scale of an instrument might be changing with time, which requires respective internal auditing procedures to register and initiate a recalibration.
- Evaluation of the dependence of the responsivity on the temperature and humidity, through the characterization of the sensitivity coefficients.
- Validation of data processing and software, by comparison with other references, such reference sources, measurement results by a reference spectroradiometer, or ground-truth references in the case of EO applications.

Complementary procedures

There are several other properties of spectroradiometers that might be relevant for very specific applications and need to complement the characterization of the instrument to avoid errors caused by the respective effects:

- Evaluation of the dependence of the responsivity on the geometrical conditions of the irradiation, by characterizing the dependence on the incidence angle, which is relevant for the measurements of extended sources, such as global spectral irradiance (direct and scattered by the atmosphere) of the sun.
- Evaluation of the dependence of the responsivity on the polarization state of the irradiation, by characterizing the variation under different polarization conditions, which might be relevant when highly polarized sources are measured.
- Evaluation of the uniformity of the responsivity at the collection area, by characterizing the spatial variation with a small spot.
- Evaluation of the sensitivity to blooming, which is relevant e.g. for HDR measurements.
- Evaluation of the sensitivity to leakage, which might be an issue for measurements at very short integration times.

Additional procedures for specific end-user applications

Additional procedures can be required for specific end-user application:

- **Spectral solar measurements using the sun as transfer radiant source:**
 - At wavelengths shorter than 315 nm: Straylight at short wavelengths in the UV-B is an issue with single monochromators (even with the straylight matrix correction this does not resolve sufficiently the problem), and it is required for scanning double monochromators. This type of work started in 2002 and is ongoing (Transportable reference spectroradiometer QASUME, [Gröbner 2005, Hülsen 2016], Calibration and Measurement Capability (CMC) on spectral solar UV irradiance calibration in the key comparison database, KCDB, by PMOD/WRC). The adaptation of these procedures for array spectroradiometers must be studied.
 - For spectral solar measurements at longer wavelengths than the UV-B (wavelengths longer than approximately 315 nm), similar procedures as employed with QASUME can be applied, using also to some extent single monochromators, and perhaps array spectroradiometers. Spectral regions with large spectral gradients might need special treatment regarding straylight.
- **Measurement of spectral narrowband sources (e.g. LEDs):** For the measurement of narrowband sources like LEDs a spectral bandpass characterization and correction is needed in order to achieve low uncertainties. This is as well true if such a narrowband source is used for the radiometric calibration of the transfer standard spectroradiometer. In [CIE 2014] such methods for correction are described. This shows that additional procedures might be needed due to the use of the source measured in the application, but also during calibration.
- **Solar cells:** Sun simulators, as used in solar cell indoor testing applications, nowadays usually consist of either a single xenon (Xe) lamp, a xenon halogen (Ha) lamp combination or a combination of light-emitting-diodes (LEDs) of different wavelengths. Especially for sun simulators having a xenon

lamp a bandwidth correction and such a characterization of bandpass is strongly recommended. In addition, as solar cells are large-area devices (up to 210 mm x 210 mm), the lateral uniformity of the measurement plane has to be characterized.

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Annex A Illustration of the different effects on the transfer

In the first stage of the transfer, the spectroradiometer is calibrated in spectral irradiance with respect to a transfer radiant source which provides very favorable conditions for this calibration (smooth spectral distribution, high irradiance and stability). It is exemplified in Figure 1, where a radiant source with the CIE standard illuminant A spectral distribution is used as transfer radiant source (see spectral distribution in Figure 1.a). When this radiant source is measured with a spectroradiometer with the true responsivity shown in Figure 1.b, it is expected a response as shown in Figure 1.c (expressed in units of digital numbers, DN, or counts, cts), with an integration time of 1 second. However, during the measurement process some errors are added and some restrictions are imposed, and this ideal response is never attained. To start with, it is not possible to use so high integration time, because the detector response would saturate. When the integration time is decreased 1000 times, as in the example shown in Figure 1.d, less photoelectrons are available, and the shot noise is more apparent in relative terms (the shot noise is the noise intrinsically due to the process of counting photoelectrons, and it follows a Poisson statistic, where the value of the variance equals the value of the average). It can be observed in the response (Figure 1.d), and consequently in the measured responsivity (Figure 1.e), which is calculated as a dark-subtracted averaged response, divided by the integration time, corrected from non-linearity, calibrated for wavelength, and divided by the known irradiance of the transfer radiant source. The relative error shown in Figure 1.f is due mainly to shot noise, and it is larger for lower number of photoelectrons, directly related to irradiance, responsivity, integration time and number of repetitions. The number of repetitions at a given integration time allows the exposure to increase and the relative error to decrease. The uncertainty due to this error is added to the uncertainty of the spectral irradiance of the transfer standard (u_{ref}), but ideally can be made negligible by increasing the exposure.

Figure 1: Example of calibration of a spectroradiometer in spectral irradiance using a radiant source with the CIE standard illuminant A spectral distribution.

The transfer of the spectral irradiance is accomplished using the measured responsivity of the spectroradiometer, simply by measuring the spectral irradiance of other radiant sources at other conditions. A perfect transfer wouldn't increase the uncertainty above u_{ref} . However, it is not always possible, because the measurement conditions might be much less favorable than in calibration conditions (external stray light, different temperature or relative humidity, less available exposure), and because the spectral distribution of the radiant source to be measured might have a larger irradiance range or contain larger curvatures.

The requirements of the spectroradiometer need to include those to deal with this situation, in order to correct these sources of errors below u_{ref} , or the target uncertainty of the specific application.

When the irradiance range to be used is too large, the non-linearity needs to be correctable, and then it is convenient to have direct access to raw responses and integration times. When the spectral distribution to be measured contains large curvatures, the effect of the finite size of the measurement intervals is a source of error. In the case of the spectroradiometers, this effect, with origin in the bandpass and the internal stray light, can be characterized by the Line Spread Function (LSF). It makes that a line is not only a line but it is located with some extension around a wavelength. An example of LSF (2.2 nm of FWHM) is given in Figure 2, with the model used in the following figure. This function convolves the spectral distribution to be measured through the measurement process.

Figure 2: Line Spread Function (LSF) with 2.2 nm of FWHM.

Spectral irradiance measurements of six radiant sources with spectral distributions as six CIE illuminants (A, D65, LED-B3, LED-RGB1, FL1 and HP1) were simulated and the comparison with respect to the true value is shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4, (direct comparisons on the left and relative errors on the right). It can be observed that the error increased at positions with larger curvatures, meaning that the effect of the bandpass and the internal stray light (LSF) is the most relevant source of error in the transfer when the spectral distributions to be measured contain large curvatures. In other cases, noise and non-linearity should be the most notable sources of errors.

Figure 3: Spectral irradiance measurements (left) and relative errors (right) of three radiant sources with spectral distribution as three CIE illuminants (A, D65 and LED-B3).

Figure 4: Spectral irradiance measurements (left) and relative errors (right) of three radiant sources with spectral distributions as three CIE illuminants (LED-RGB1, FL1 and HP1).

For a closer insight into the impact of the LSF, results of simulated measurements with different FWHMs are shown in Figure 5. The left plot shows the direct comparison of the measurements with FWHMs of 0.2 nm, 2.2 nm and 4.4 nm. On the middle, the relative error with respect to the true value is shown. Finally, on the right plot, the second derivative of the illuminant, relative to the value of the illuminant is represented. This last plot, and its comparison with the relative errors shown in the middle plot, shows that the error due to the effect of the bandpass and the internal stray light can be predicted simply by the knowledge of the illuminant and the LSF of the spectroradiometer.

Figure 5: Results of simulated measurements with different FWHMs. The left plot shows the direct comparison of the measurements with FWHMs of 0.2 nm, 2.2 nm and 4.4 nm. The middle plot shows the relative error with respect to the true value. Finally, on the right plot, the second derivative of the illuminant, relative to the value of the illuminant, is represented.

In Figure 6, results of simulated measurements with different non-linearity levels are shown. The top plot shows the direct comparison of the measurements with different values of the parameter used to simulate the non-linearity. The bottom plot shows the relative error with respect to the true value. For this example, where we have used a model of non-linearity with decreasing responsivity for higher response, it is clearly observed that it results in a variation of the relative values of the relative maxima, whereas the lowest values are not greatly affected.

Figure 6: Results of simulated measurements with different levels of non-linearity. The top plot shows the direct comparison of the measurements with different values of the parameter used to simulate the non-linearity. The bottom plot shows the relative error with respect to the true value.